

Nomenclatural Novelties in Aloaceae

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NEW TAXA PROPOSED HERE

×*Alonaloë*, ×*Alostaloë*, ×*Aristeria*, ×*Goniloba*

×*Alonialoë desmetiana*, ×*Aristeria bedinghausii*, ×*Aristeria beguinii*, ×*Aristeria lapaixii*, ×*Aristeria nowotnyi*, ×*Gastonialoë pfrimmeri*, ×*Gastonialoë radlii*, ×*Gastonialoë rebutii*, ×*Gastonialoë sculptilis*, ×*Gastonialoë smaragdina*, ×*Gastonialoë pethamensis*, ×*Gonimara corderoyi*

In 2014 James S. Boatwright and John Charles Manning transferred *Aloë*¹ *aristata* to the monotypic genus *Aristaloë* and *Aloë dinteri*, *Aloë sladeniana* and *Aloë variegata* to *Gonialoë*. 2013 saw the revival of *Kumara*, a genus to which *Aloë disticha* var. *plicatilis* and *Aloë haemanthifolia* were assigned.

These changes necessitate several new nothogenera for intergeneric hybrids involving these species, two of which, ×*Gastonialoë* and ×*Gonimara*, have already been proposed.

¹ ICN Art. 60.7 allows the use of diaeresis (ë) indicating that a vowel is to be pronounced separately from the preceding vowel. In Latin, *Aloë* has three syllables.

The following new nothogenera, combinations and cultivars are proposed here:

×**Alonialoë**

×**Alonialoë** M.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.** = *Aloë* L. × *Gonialoë* (Baker) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning

×	<i>Gonialoë sladeniana</i>	<i>Gonialoë variegata</i>
<i>Aloë bakeri</i>		‘Lysa’
<i>Aloë descoingsii</i>	‘Tiny Gem’	‘Versad’
<i>Aloë humilis</i>		<i>desmetiana</i>
<i>Aloë myriacantha</i>	‘Exocet’	
<i>Aloë rauhii</i> × <i>Aloë bellatula</i>	‘Midas’	

×**Alonialoë desmetiana** (Baker) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.** = *Aloë humilis* (L.) Mill. × *Gonialoë variegata* (L.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning = *Aloë desmetiana* Baker – Fl. Cap. (Harvey) 6(2): 329. 1896

×**Alostaloë**

×**Alostaloë** M.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.** = *Aloë* L. × *Aristaloë* Boatwr. & J.C.Manning

×	<i>Aristaloë aristata</i>
<i>Aloë erinacea</i>	‘Tegelberg’s Triumph’

×**Aristeria**

×**Aristeria** M.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.** = *Aristaloë* Boatwr. & J.C.Manning × *Gasteria* Duval

×	<i>Aristaloë aristata</i>
<i>Gasteria bicolor</i>	<i>lapaixii</i>
<i>Gasteria bicolor</i> var. <i>bicolor</i>	<i>lapaixii</i> nothovar. <i>lapaixii</i>
<i>Gasteria carinata</i>	<i>beguinii</i>
<i>Gasteria carinata</i> var. <i>verrucosa</i>	<i>beguinii</i> nothovar. <i>beguinii</i>
<i>Gasteria disticha</i>	<i>bedinghausii</i>
<i>Gasteria</i> 'Royal Wolfgang'	'Aurora'
<i>Gasteria</i> sp.	<i>nowotnyi</i>

×**Aristeria bedinghausii** (Radl) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.** = *Aristaloë aristata* (Haw.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning × *Gasteria disticha* (L.) Haw. = *Aloë bedinghausii* Radl – Monatsschr. Kakteenk. 1896, vi. 24 = ×*Gasteraloë bedinghausii* (Radl) Guillaumin

×**Aristeria beguinii** (Radl) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.** = *Aristaloë aristata* (Haw.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning × *Gasteria carinata* Duval = *Aloë* ×*beguinii* Radl – Monatsschr. Kakteenk. 6: 24. 1896 = ×*Gasteraloë beguinii* (Radl) Guillaumin

×**Aristeria beguinii nothovar. beguinii** = *Aristaloë aristata* (Haw.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning × *Gasteria carinata* var. *verrucosa* (Mill.) van Jaarsv.

Aloë ×beguinii was published by Radl as *Aloë longiaristata* × *Gasteria verrucosa*, but if the latter is considered a variety of *Gasteria carinata* it must have nothovarietal rank (ICN Art. H.5.2²). As a nothospecies it is nevertheless the correct name for all hybrids between *Aristaloë aristata* and *Gasteria carinata* (ICN Art. H.5.2 Note 1³ and Ex. 1⁴).

×***Aristeria lapaixii*** (Radl) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.** = *Aristaloë aristata* (Haw.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning × *Gasteria bicolor* Haw. = *Aloë lapaixii* Radl – Monatsschr. Kakteenk. 1896, vi. 24. = ×*Gasteraloë lapaixii* (Radl) Guillaumin

×***Aristeria lapaixii*** nothovar. ***lapaixii*** = *Aristaloë aristata* (Haw.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning × *Gasteria bicolor* Haw. var. *bicolor* = *Aloë lapaixii* Radl – Monatsschr. Kakteenk. 1896, vi. 24. = ×*Gasteraloë lapaixii* (Radl) Guillaumin

Aloë lapaixii was published by Radl as *Aloë longiaristata* × *Gasteria maculata*, but if the latter is considered a synonym of *Gasteria bicolor* var. *bicolor* it must have nothovarietal rank (ICN Art. H.5.2). As a nothospecies it is nevertheless the correct name for all hybrids between *Aristaloë aristata* and *Gasteria bicolor* (ICN Art. H.5.2 Note 1 and Ex. 1).

² ‘If the postulated or known parent taxa are at unequal ranks, the appropriate rank of the nothotaxon is the lowest of these ranks.’

³ ‘When a nothotaxon is designated by a name at a rank inappropriate to its hybrid formula, the name is incorrect in relation to that hybrid formula but may nevertheless be correct, or may become correct later (see also Art. 52 Note 4).’

⁴ ‘The combination *Elymus ×laxus* (Fr.) Melderis & D. C. McClint. (in *Watsonia* 14: 394. 1983), based on *Triticum laxum* Fr. (Novit. Fl. Suec. Mant. 3: 13. 1842), was published for hybrids with the formula *E. farctus* subsp. *boreoatlanticus* (Simonet & Guin.) Melderis × *E. repens* (L.) Gould, so that the combination is at a rank inappropriate to the hybrid formula. It is, however, the correct name applicable to all hybrids between *E. farctus* (Viv.) Melderis and *E. repens*.’

×*Aristeria nowotnyi* (Radl) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.** = *Aristaloë aristata* (Haw.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning × *Gasteria* sp. = *Aloë nowotnyi* Radl – Monatschr. Kakteenk. 1896, vi. 27 = ×*Gasteraloë nowotnyi* (Radl) G.D.Rowley

×**Gastonialoë**

×**Gastonialoë** C.C.Walker = *Gasteria* Duval × *Gonialoë* (Baker) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning

×	<i>Gonialoë variegata</i>
<i>Gasteria acinacifolia</i>	<i>smaragdina</i>
<i>Gasteria batesiana</i>	‘Orella’
<i>Gasteria bicolor</i> var. <i>bicolor</i>	‘Agate Chips’
<i>Gasteria carinata</i>	<i>pethamensis</i>
<i>Gasteria carinata</i> var. <i>verrucosa</i>	<i>pethamensis</i> nothovar. <i>pethamensis</i>
<i>Gasteria</i> ×<i>cheilophylla</i>	<i>sculptilis</i>
<i>Gasteria</i> ×<i>cheilophylla</i> nothovar. <i>cheilophylla</i>	<i>sculptilis</i> nothovar. <i>sculptilis</i>
<i>Gasteria</i> ‘Old Man Silver’	‘Green Ghost’, ‘Green Ice’
<i>Gasteria</i> sp.	<i>pfrimmeri</i>
<i>Gasteria</i> sp.?	<i>radlii</i>
<i>Gasteria</i> sp.	<i>rebutii</i>

×***Gastoniaoë pfrimmeri*** (Guillaumin) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.**
 = *Goniaoë variegata* (L.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning × *Gasteria* sp. =
 ×*Gasteraloë pfrimmeri* Guillaumin – Bull. Mus. Natl. Hist. Nat.
 1931, Ser. II. iii. 339

×***Gastoniaoë radlii*** (L.E.Newton) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.** =
Goniaoë variegata (L.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning or *Aloë serrulata*
 (Aiton) Haw. × *Gasteria* sp. = ×*Gasteraloë radlii* L.E.Newton –
 Brit. Cact. Succ. J. 15(1): 34 (1997)

×***Gastoniaoë rebutii*** (hort. ex A.Berger) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.**
 = *Gasteria* sp. × *Goniaoë variegata* (L.) Boatwr. &
 J.C.Manning = *Aloë* ×*rebutii* hort. ex A.Berger – Pflanzenr.
 (Engler) Liliac.-Asphodel.-Aloin. 191, hybr. 1908 = ×*Gasteraloë*
rebutii (hort. ex A.Berger) Guillaumin

×***Gastoniaoë sculptilis*** (G.D.Rowley ex L.E.Newton) M.van der
 Meer **comb. nov.** = *Gasteria carinata* Duval × *Gasteria pulchra*
 (Aiton) Haw. × *Goniaoë variegata* (L.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning =
 ×*Gasteraloë sculptilis* G.D.Rowley ex L.E.Newton – Haseltonia 5:
 94. 1998

×***Gastoniaoë sculptilis* nothovar. *sculptilis*** = *Gasteria pulchra*
 (Aiton) Haw. × *Gasteria carinata* var. *verrucosa* (Mill.) van Jaarsv.
 × *Goniaoë variegata* (L.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning

×*Gasteraloë sculptilis* was published by Rowley as *Aloë variegata*
 × *Gasteria* ×*cheilophylla*, the latter being *Gasteria pulchra* ×
Gasteria carinata var. *verrucosa*. As hybrids involving a variety
 both nothotaxa must have nothovarietal rank (ICN Art. H.5.2). As
 nothospecies they are nevertheless the correct names for all
 hybrids with the respective formulas *Gasteria pulchra* × *Gasteria*
carinata × *Goniaoë variegata* and *Gasteria pulchra* × *Gasteria*
carinata (ICN Art. H.5.2 Note 1 and Ex. 1).

×**Gastonialoë smaragdina** (hort. ex A.Berger) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.** = *Gasteria acinacifolia* (J.Jacq.) Haw. × *Gonialoë variegata* (L.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning = *Aloë × smaragdina* A.Berger – Pflanzenr. (Engler) IV. 38 III, II (Heft 33): 190. 1908 = ×*Gasteraloë smaragdina* (hort. ex A.Berger) Guillaumin

×**Gastonialoë pethamensis** (Baker) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.** = *Gasteria carinata* Duval × *Gonialoë variegata* (L.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning = *Gasteria × pethamensis* Baker – J. Linn. Soc., Bot. 18: 193. 1880 = ×*Gasteraloë pethamensis* (Baker) G.D.Rowley

×**Gastonialoë pethamensis nothovar. pethamensis** = *Gasteria carinata* var. *verrucosa* (Mill.) van Jaarsv. × *Gonialoë variegata* (L.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning

Gasteria × pethamensis was published by Baker as *Aloë variegata* × *Gasteria verrucosa*, but if the latter is considered a variety of *Gasteria carinata* it must have nothovarietal rank (ICN Art. H.5.2). As a nothospecies it is nevertheless the correct name for all hybrids between *Gasteria carinata* and *Gonialoë variegata* (ICN Art. H.5.2 Note 1 and Ex. 1).

×**Goniloba**

×**Goniloba** M.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.** = *Astroloba Uitewaal* × *Gonialoë* (Baker) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning

×	<i>Astroloba congesta</i>	<i>Astroloba spiralis</i>
<i>Gonialoë sladeniana</i>		‘Leo’
<i>Gonialoë variegata</i>	‘Chunky’	

×**Gonimara**

×**Gonimara** Gideon F.Sm. & Molteno = *Gonialoë* (Baker) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning × *Kumara* Medik.

×	<i>Kumara plicatilis</i>
<i>Gonialoë variegata</i>	<i>corderoyi</i>

×**Gonimara corderoyi** (Berger) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.** = *Gonialoë variegata* (L.) Boatwr. & J.C.Manning × *Kumara plicatilis* (L.) G.D.Rowley = *Aloë* × *corderoyi* Berger – Monatsz. f. Kakteenk. (1904) 14: 61

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